

Management

SELF-EVALUATION OF GAMBELLA UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The major objective of this study was to investigate the quality of education, research and service delivery in Gambella University. To realize this objective, the summary write up was deployed the qualitative presentation of data and statistical records presentation of certain data of numerical values. Descriptive and explanatory research technique was also employed to narrate the audit outcomes. Systematic approaches using the computational techniques – SPSS and Excel 2010 has been used in the process of data analysis. This institutional quality audit report has provided a description and evaluation of the quality of Gambella University educational provision and of its mechanisms for assuring quality and relevance.

Keywords: Quality of Education; Teaching and Learning; Vision; Mission; Goals; Research, Community Based Education.

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1. Introduction

1.1. The Institution

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) has implemented tremendous development changes in the country and one of the policies designed by the government to bring about rapid and sustainable development is the education and training policy. As it is known there were only two public universities in Ethiopia twenty years ago. Now, the number of public learning institutes have increased more than 35 in the country, among them is the Gambella University which is situated in Gambella People National Regional State (GPNRS) is one of the recently established higher education institutions in Ethiopia. Its cornerstone was laid by FDRE Prime Minister Hailemariam Desalegn and GPNRS president Gatluak Tut on 28th April, 2014.

Gambella University is located at Gambella town, the capital of GPNRS which is 766 km far from Addis Ababa. At the beginning the institution was established as Gambella Agricultural, Technical, Vocational and Educational Training (GATVET) College which was organized and managed by the former Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and GPNRS and Bureau of Agriculture and Rural Development from 2002 to 2012 to produce middle level Agricultural Developmental Agents. During ten years (2002-2012) more than 1,950 students were graduated on Animal Science, Natural Resource, Plant Science and Cooperative Departments in the Diploma program / (level IV). Moreover, more than 493 General Agriculture students were graduated within the Certificate Program.

Later on, based on the agreement made between the Ministry of Education and Regional stakeholders, it was affiliated with Mettu University and become the College of Agriculture and Natural Resource campus from 2012 to 2013/14 with (Animal Science, Plant Science, Natural Resource Management and Agricultural Economics) departments. As an independent institution Gambella University was proclaimed by the Ministry of Council under Proclamation No. 317/2006 and assumes its institutional mandate. Right after, the establishment of Gambella University in 2014 opened a new chapter in the history of the Gambella Region and the people. Soon after, the University was introduced to the public and 514 students were assigned to study in College of Agriculture and Natural Resource and Faculty of Business and Economics with thirteen Departments and currently there are 27 undergraduate programs under College of Agriculture and Natural Resource, Faculty of Business and Economics, Faculty of Humanity and Computational science, Faculty of Engineering and School of law. Additionally, the university already launch Postgraduate Program in Animal Production independently and three Postgraduate programs (Project Planning and Management, Development Studies and Master of Business Administration) in collaboration with Green Research Development Institute (GRDI).

Even though Gambella University is at its infancy stage, the host region has potential and gifted natural resources (Livestock, Fish, Apiculture, Park, Soil, Forest, Multi Crops and Minerals) and internally committed academic, supporting staff and reliable stakeholders. Based on the university's strategic plan GmU is 'envisaging to be one of the recognized academic and research center in Africa by 2030' in its core four strategic pillars namely Educational Quality and Relevance, Research and Technology Transfer, Community Service and Partnership, and Good Governance of the university is to realize it's given mission by HEI Proclamation No. 650/2009 Article no. 4.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the Study Area

Table 1: Students enrollment data in undergraduate and postgraduate programs (regular, weekend and summer) in the year 2016/17

Program	Number of students				Total	Remark
	Male	%	Female	%		
Regular undergraduate	1178	58.2	846	41.8	2024	*
Weekend undergraduate	1025	85	188	15	1213	
Summer undergraduate	516	86	87	14	603	
Total undergraduate students	2719	71	1121	29	3840	
Regular postgraduate	-	-	-	-	-	**

Weekend postgraduate	103	95	5	5	108	
Total postgraduate Students	103	95	5	5	108	
Total	2822	71	1126	29	3948	

*In year 2016/17 College of Agriculture and Natural Resource have not enrolled students due to ENEA placement technical problem.

**There is no regular post graduate students' enrolled in this year due to late announcement to MOE and media.

Table 2: Undergraduate Programs offered under each College/Faculties/School in GmU

College/Faculties/School	Programs Offered
College of Agriculture and Natural Resource	Agro-Economics Animal Production and Health Disaster and Risk Management Studies Horticulture Natural Resource Management Plant Science Rural Development and Agricultural Extension Water Shed and Soil Conservation Wildlife and Eco-Tourism Management
Faculty of Business and Economics	Accounting and Finance Cooperative Business Management Economics Logistic and Supply Chain Management Management Marketing Management Public Administration
Faculty of Humanity and Computational Sciences	Biology Chemistry Computer Science English Language and Literature Gender and Development Studies Mathematics Sociology and Social Anthropology Statistics
Faculty of Engineering	Civil Engineering Food Engineering
School of Law	Law

Table 3: Post Graduate Programs offered by GmU SGS

Regular Post Graduate	Weekend Post Graduate*
Animal production	Project Planning and Management Development Studies: Specialization in Disaster Risk Management and Food Security Studies Master of Business Administration-MBA

*This program is being offered by the collaboration of GmU and GRDI.

Table 4: Academic-Staff Profile of each Department

Departments	PhD	MSc/MA	BSc/ BA/DVM	Technical Ass. Diploma	Total	Remark
Accounting and Finance	2	1	8	-	11	
Agro-Economics	2	2	9	-	13	
Animal production and health	1	11	12	3	27	
Biology	-	3	-	-	3	
Chemistry	-	1	-	-	1	
Civil Engineering	-	1	4	-	5	
Computer Science	-	3	5	-	8	
Cooperatives	-	6	-	2	8	
Disaster Risk Managt	-	1	3	-	4	
Economics	2	4	4	-	10	
English	-	7	2	-	9	
Food Engineering	-	2	2	-	4	
Gender and Dev't study	-	3	1	-	4	
Horticulture	-	5	4	1	10	
Law	1	1	2	-	4	
Logistic & Sup. Ch. Magt	-	1	-	-	1	
Management	-	7	-	-	7	
Marketing management	1	1	-	-	2	
Mathematics	-	6	4	-	10	
Natural Resource Man't	1	11	10	4	26	
Plant Science	1	5	9	-	15	
Psychology	-	-	4	-	4	
Public Administration	3	2	4	-	9	
Rural-Dev't and Agri-Ext	-	5	3	-	8	
Sociology and Social AT	-	3	2	-	5	
Soil Res. and Water Mang't	-	4	2	-	6	
Statistics	-	-	2	-	2	
Wild Life and Eco-tu	1	4	6	-	11	
Total	17	104	99	10	230	

Table 5: Regular Student Enrolment Data

	2012/13	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17
College of Agriculture and Natural Resource	207	277	257	499	-
Faculty of Business& Economics	-	-	276	289	343
Faculty of Humanities& Comp. Sc	-	-	-	57	326
Faculty of Engineering	-	-	-	-	43
School of Law	-	-	-	41	56
School of Graduate Studies	-	-	-	-	-
Total	207	277	533	886	768

Table 6: Weekend Student Enrolment Data

	2012/13	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17
College of Agriculture and Natural Resource	152	92	126	82	
Faculty of Business& Economics	-	-	173	467	

Faculty of Humanities and Computational Sciences	-	-	-	-	1213
Faculty of Engineering	-	-	-	-	
School of Law	-	-	-	-	
School of Graduate Studies	-	-	-	-	108
Total	152	92	299	549	1321

NB: 712 (first year), 334 (second year), 138 (third year), 29 (fourth year)

Table 7: Summer School Student Enrolment Data

	2012/13	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17
College of Agriculture and natural resource	286	56	108	57	*
Faculty of Business& Economics	-	-	45	76	-
Faculty of Humanities and Computational Sciences	-	-	-	-	-
Faculty of Engineering	-	-	-	-	-
School of Law	-	-	-	17	
School of Graduate Studies	-	-	-	-	-
Total	286	56	153	150	603

NB: *No enrollment in this academic year, however registrar records show that 150 (fist year), 253 (second year), 46 (third year), 154 (fourth year)

Table 8: List of students' enrolment in each department under regular program

S.N	Departments	Year I			Year II			Year III			G/Total		
		M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
1	Rural-Dev't and Agri-Ext				31	20	51	12	13	25	43	33	76
2	Plant Science				27	29	56	10	21	31	37	50	87
3	Agro-Economics				30	27	57	18	15	33	48	42	90
4	Animal Science				27	13	40	11	15	26	38	28	66
5	Natural Resource Man't				25	22	47	12	9	21	37	31	68
6	Wild Life and Eco-tours.				25	13	38	7	12	19	32	25	57
7	Soil Res. and Water shed Mgt.				33	24	57	14	11	25	47	35	82
8	Disaster Risk Managt				24	29	53	16	11	27	40	40	80
9	Horticulture				24	23	47				24	23	47
10	Accounting and Finance	30	26	56	40	13	53	33	27	60	103	66	169
11	Economics	45	4	49	39	12	51	23	25	48	107	41	148
12	Public Administration	34	10	44	30	12	42	24	16	40	88	38	126
13	Cooperatives	34	13	47	28	7	35	12	19	31	74	39	113
14	Management	26	30	56	25	37	62	22	29	51	73	96	169
15	Logistic & Sup. Ch. Magt	42	6	48	27	9	36				69	15	84
16	Marketing management	22	21	43							22	21	43

17	Biology	23	24	47							23	24	47
18	Chemistry	27	12	39							27	12	39
19	Statistics	21	19	40							21	19	40
20	Computer Science	26	12	38							26	12	38
21	Mathematics	11	9	20	7	10	17				18	19	37
22	Gender and Dev't study	26	32	58							26	32	58
23	Sociology and Social AT	25	29	54							25	29	54
24	English	23	7	30	19	21	40				42	28	70
25	Law	38	18	56	27	10	37				65	28	93
26	Civil & Food engineering	23	20	43							23	20	43
	Grand Total	476	292	768	488	331	819	214	223	437	1178	846	2024

2.2. Governance, Leadership and Organizational Structure

The effectiveness of the governance and management system of a higher education institution is crucial for the delivery of quality and relevant education. According to higher education proclamation number 650/2009, part three section one Article 43; any higher education institution shall consist of the following governing and advisory bodies: (a) the Board; (b) President; (c) Senate; (d) Managing Council; (e) University Council; (f) Academic Unit Council; (g) Academic Unit Managing Council; (h) Department Assembly; (i) Advisory or specialized committees or councils that may be established by the board, senate or university council. According to the GmU senate legislation (May, 2015, p.5), which is the latest version, the senate has a wide representation and consist of the following voting members chaired by the President. (i) The President, (ii) The Vice-Presidents, (iii) The ICT Scientific Director, (iv) The Student Service Director, (v) Director for Academic Programs, (vi) Quality Assurance Director, (vii) Research and Development Director¹, (viii) Director for Technology Transfer¹, (ix) Corporate Communications & Marketing Director¹, (x) Heads/Deans of Colleges, (xi) Selected heads of Academic units and Meritorious, (xii) Senior academic staff (not exceeding 15), (xiii) Two representatives from academic staff, (xiv) Two representatives (Male and Female) of the student union, and (xv) The University Registrar.

The Senate functions through different standing Committees: Academic Standards and Quality Assurance Committee (ASQAC); Admissions and Placement Committee (APC); Research and Development Committee (RDC); Academic Staff Affairs Committee (ASAC); Students' Affairs Committee (SAC); The duties and responsibilities of the various committees and office holders of the University are also set out in the Gambella University Senate Legislation (2015).

3. Institutional Self Evaluation and Methodology

3.1. Institutional Self-Evaluation in Brief

¹Research and Development Director¹, Director for Technology Transfer¹, Corporate Communications & Marketing Director¹ do not exist in the current organizational structure however, the first three are functional under the office of directorate of research and community service.

Institutional Self-Evaluation attempt was made by GmUs' Education Relevance and Quality Assurance Directorate to conduct self-evaluation in 2015/16 academic year. Unlikely, due to some constraints the attempt has failed to reach its goal. As the core responsibility, the Directorate Office has made a further effort to realize the plan in 2016/17. In this regard, the office adopted a plan to carry on the task using the internal resources personnel and established SED Team consisting of five (5) members in coordination with the Academic Vice President Office of Gambella University as per HERQA Document reference QA03/06/V1.

Table 9: Audit Team Members and their responsibilities

S/No.	Name	Rank	Responsibility in the Team	Remark
1	Tamrat Dina	Lecturer	Chair Person	ERQA- Director
2	Dr. Jemberu Alemu	Asst. Professor	Secretary	STS
3	Luke Kue	Lecturer	Member	FBE
4	Aregay Berhe	Lecturer	Member	Engineering Faculty
5	Endalkachew Taye	Lecturer	Member	HCS Faculty

Gambella University began its institutional journey by adopting nationally harmonized curricula for each program. In the last two years, the university hasn't done much program review with exception of Animal Science Department which was initiated based on the complaint that often comes from the students and other stakeholders on marketability of the field. To address this, the university established a team of experts and conduct assessment and investigate the matter to account for the demand of the potential employers whose their final assessment outcome were endorsed by the University's Senate.

Based on the result and recommendations of the team of experts, alternatives were presented to the faculty and the university's Academic Commission (AC). Then, the AC evaluated the result and finally the senate approved the modification of the department from Animal Science to Animal Production and Health.

Internal quality audit is a vital activity to know drawbacks and achievements of any educational institution. As strategy, the Team has used Higher Education Relevance and Quality Agency (HERQA) Self Evaluation Document (SED) Preparation and Audit manuals as a base line for the document preparation. Term of Reference (TOR) and Document Preparation plan were developed by the team as guidelines for internal quality audit of the University. Then, emphasis was placed on the ten (10) focus areas identified by HERQA and developed to gather the data from University Community that basically involve the Academic, Administration Staffs and Students.

3.2. Methodology

For data collection and analysis both qualitative and quantitative methods were employed and various techniques such as questionnaire survey, semi-structured interview, Focus Group Discussion (FGD), secondary document review and analysis and observations were carried out as data collection tool.

The audit team used three types of questionnaires designed and filled by students, Instructors and administrative support staffs of GmU. Interviews were carried out with top and key management personnel to gather their opinions and reflections on the University self-performance for the past

two years. Focus group discussions were also held with various academic and administration staffs to obtain comprehensive information and identify the competing motions. The audit team reviewed relevant documents such as University Senate Legislation, Higher Education Institution Proclamation, The University Five Year Strategic Plan, Program Evaluation Guideline, Reports, etc. and other Documents used by the respective Departments. The Audit team conducted observation on classrooms, students' cafeteria, clinic, stores, workshop, library, laboratories etc.

3.2.1. Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

To collect comprehensive data and opinion from university community, the team preferred purposive sampling technique that targeted the students, instructors and administrative support staffs that was randomly selected with consideration on ability and capacity of filling questioners. Regarding the sample size, the team selected a total of 100 students, 45 instructors and 75 administrative support staffs². Questionnaires distribution was stratified along the total number of students in respective of the level of their academic year. For instance, from second and third year, sample proportional to the total number of the student enrolled in each department was considered taking their duration of stay in the campus as resources that empower them a confident and knowledge to give a fruitful responses and inputs.

Table 10: Sample Size Distribution

S/No.	Respondents	Category	Total Population	Sample Size	%
1	Students	Regular	2024	75	3.71
		Weekend	1321	25	1.89
2	Academic	Instructor	230	45	19.57
		Others			
3	Administration*	All level	566	75	13.25
Total			4141	220	5.31 (5.60)

*The Administration staffs include 355 fixed staffs and 211 contract staffs (Source: Gambella University payroll – February 2017)

Group discussion was designed to compose 45 Academic and Administration staffs; however, 35 personnel participated in the panel. The panel were also further divided into three sub-groups to maximize the participation and finally brought in to final session to reflect their respective group discussions in general panel. Fifteen top and middle level management personnel were also separately interviewed.

3.2.2. Data Analysis Method

Data analysis involved both qualitative and quantitative techniques and questionnaires were administered with SPSS IBM v20 software. Group discussions and interviews were transcribed, consolidated and narrated into each focus areas that are the main part of the assessment. Various secondary documents, reports, Brouchers, etc. were collected and analyzed to capture the historical and brief of the institutional process and setup.

²From 1st, 2nd -3rd year regular students and from weekend BSc and PG students and also

4. Data Analysis

4.1. The Evaluation of Quality and Relevance

Quality and relevance assessment is a litmus test for institutional self-audit to identify achievements, challenges, good practice and possible improvements. As per the ten focus areas identified by HERQA, the following sections will analyze the assessment outcomes from various university communities.

4.1.1. *Vision, Mission and Goals*

Gambella University was established as part of legal higher educational body by Council of Minister Regulation No. 317/2014. Besides, national prescribed objectives under Higher Education Proclamation No. 650/2009 Article 4 (1-9) which guided the university mission, it's observed from various documents, reports, etc. analyzed that the vision is 'envisaging to be one of the Recognized Academic and Research Centers in Africa by 2030'.

The mission of Gambella university which is analyzed from different documents presented as follows:-'providing quality education and training to address the community need through innovation, problem-solving research engagement, and enhancing conducive working environment to produce trained and competent citizens' (Magazine of Gambella University and the Region, 2015: 9). In the other source, the mission was described as 'providing quality education and training to address the community need through innovation, research engagement, and enhancing conducive working environment so as to produce trained and competitive citizen' (University's Billboard, 2016). On the other hand (Strategic Plan, 2015: 17), outlined that the mission of the University as 'intensely committed to provide high quality academic and training to produce competent and ethical citizens and enhance modern technology and problem-solving researchers that contribute to the region and country development'.

Gambella University is established of seventeen sets of goals that are run through four pillars – namely Education Relevance and Quality, Research and Technology Transfer, Community Services and Partnership, and Operational and Administrative Excellence. These include; (1) increase competent graduates, (2) increase customers satisfaction, (3) increase revenue generation, (4) improve budget utilization, (5) strengthen and enhance educational equity and accessibility, (6) enhance academic quality and relevance, (7) develop relevant and qualify staffs, (8) improve technological infrastructure, (9) improve resources utilization and assets management, (9) enhance technology package development and linkages with industry, (10) improve community and stakeholders partnership, (11) diversify and improve programs or services, (12) improve working environment and organizational culture, (13) improve knowledge, skills, motivation, and professional ethics of the staffs, and (15) improve necessary infrastructures and facilities (Source: Gambella University Web page).³

³www.gmu.edu.et and also see Strategic Plan 2015-2020 Revised Amharic version which was adopted from English version that was developed May 2015:

In other version, the strategic initiatives or goals are set to be twelve that includes (1) increase satisfaction of customers, (2) increase service beneficiaries or users, (3) increase internal revenue, (4) improve resources utilization and assets management, (5) enhance academic quality and relevance, (6) strengthen and enhance educational equity and accessibility, (7) enhance technology package development and linkages with industries, (8) improve community and stakeholders partnership, (9) diversify and improve programs or services, (10) improve working environment and organizational culture, (11) improve knowledge, skills, motivation and professional ethics of the staffs, and (12) to improve necessary infrastructure and facility.⁴

From the sixty four respondents' of administration and academics staffs, the survey indicates that 92.2% are aware of the existing documented statement of vision, mission, and goals, while 4.7% are not aware and 3.1% are uncertain. However, it is noted from questionnaires that only few of them were able to describe the vision, mission, and goals in written form. 84.4% of respondents stated that the current vision, mission, and goals meet the need of national and stakeholders. Around 89.1% have confirm that the existing Strategic Plan can help the University to achieves its plan, vision, missions, and goals.

Currently, the university has seventeen operational objectives under four pillars.⁵ To create a better holistic understanding among the university community, many awareness creations were done, however, the Audit Team observed lack of uniformity on the mission, vision, goals, and values of the Gambella University. For instance, the University Website, Billboards, and Brouchers have indicated some inconsistency.

4.1.2. Governance and Management System/Leadership

As it's clearly stated under the Higher Education Proclamation No. 650/2009 article 43(1), the Gambella University governing and advisory bodies is structured in a kind that include (a) the board, (b) president, (c) senate, (d) managing council, (d) university council and (e) academic unit council respectively. Based on article 44 of the Proclamation, "the board of a public institution shall be the supreme governing body of the institution". This implies that GmU's supreme governing body is the board of the University. Under the supervision of the board the President is assigned as Chief Executive Officer (CEO) that mandated the execution of day-to-day activities of the University according to article 53. Currently, the University is organized of two Vice Presidents, and ten Directorates that are directly accountable to the President. The Vice Presidents are in charge of the Academic and Administration. The Academic Vice President is structured with six directorates and five deans while the Administration vice president consists of four directorates. The organizational structure is sketched to function with 1,369 staffs⁶.

The primary source of job description of the top level management bodies (i.e. Presidents, Senate, Council, etc) are clearly delineated under proclamation No 650/2009 in part three section1 (article 42 - 58). The university's legislation noticeably outline the academic staffs roles and responsibilities while supporting staffs has been adopted in different guidelines and directives

⁴ See BSC Oriented Strategic plan for Gambella University, 2015: 64. Gambella

⁵ In the Strategic Plan, 2015 there were only twelve strategic goals which was later on revised to include additional five in 2016/17 fiscal year plan.

⁶ This figure represented administration and support staff required by organization structure and only 574 positions are currently filled with staffs. Also see Gambella University 2016/17 Second Quarter Report.

that entails job descriptions, placements and levels from ministry of civil service. Human Resource Directorate of the university is mandated to inform every employee about their duties and responsibilities as per the above documents and Deans and Faculty heads are responsible for staffs in the Academic wings.

Regarding the planning and decision making processes, the university has adopted various mechanisms and plate forms that involve Senate, Management, and councils meetings and assemblies that ensure participation of various internal organs including the student council to represent the students' voices. Based on the directives adopted from the higher education proclamation No. 650/2009 article 37/1 (h), (i), and the Gambella University legislation article 8 (5.13) also dictated the participation of various representatives – teachers, students and administration staffs in decision making to ensure transparency. Final documents (i.e. legislation, strategic plan, fiscal plan, etc) are passed through institutional evaluations that are approved by consensus.

In regards to incorporation of student's representative and their views or opinion in decision making on the behalf of the university, one of the interviewee narrated that;

The students are supposed to express their voice through council which has actually been established but they are not active as expected. Senate legislation also requires or dictates that the students' voices should be represent. In the Council, their representatives are always invite to participate in the decision making process and was expected to come up with agenda. They are also invited to take part in student disciplinary committee but are not taking active roles.

Survey also indicated that 78.1% of the respondents believed that the University has functional governing bodies and 68.8% stated that Gambella University has appropriate and effectives governance and organizational structure which can allow the University to achieve its aspired vision, mission, and goals. 71.9% of the respondents explain that they are aware of their job description, responsibilities and roles.

The University communicates its comprehensive plans, reports and decisions for all members of the community through meetings and notices. Regarding new and adopted guidelines and policies are communicated through official letters and notices. 62.5% of the employee involved in the survey confirmed that they are aware of how decisions are made in the University. However, 45.3% witnessed the representation of staffs and students in decision making process while 40.6% do not.

In general, the above mentioned organizational structure is adopted in a believe that its in line with the existing institutional vision, mission, goals and current institutional carrier structure or size.

4.1.3. Infrastructure and Learning Resources

The university commenced its tasks on already existing build academic institution. In the last two years, the University has built additional blocks for dormitories, class rooms, etc. and there are also ongoing constructions. To investigate the existing of adequate infrastructures and facilities in

the University, the Audit teams have developed questionnaires and conducted interviews on three prospective.

Table 11: Physical Facilities – The Administration Staffs Response⁷

Facilities	Accessibility				Utilization				Quality			
	High	Moderate	Low	Total	High	Fair	Poor	Total	Good	Less	Poor	Total
Classrooms	37.9	51.8	10.3	100	45.8	44.0	10.2	100	56.1	31.6	12.3	100
Offices	32.1	46.4	21.4	100	33.3	48.1	18.5	100	44.6	42.9	12.5	100
Lecture hall	28.6	30.3	41.1	100	41.5	22.7	35.8	100	35.2	35.2	29.6	100
Dining hall	14.5	43.6	41.8	100	20.4	33.3	46.3	100	18.5	40.7	40.7	100
Furniture	23.2	33.7	40.1	100	27.5	31.4	41.2	100	33.3	44.4	22.2	100
SF – T	5.4	25.0	69.6	100	9.1	29.1	31.8	100	1.8	31.6	66.7	100
CMF	6.9	44.8	48.3	100	12.5	35.7	51.8	100	10.5	47.4	42.1	100
Cafeteria	12.5	39.3	48.2	100	8.8	49.1	42.1	100	8.9	30.4	60.7	100
Dormitories	33.9	51.8	14.3	100	31.6	49.1	19.3	100	44.6	35.8	19.6	100
Sport field	15.8	15.8	68.4	100	8.9	32.1	58.9	100	10.3	32.8	56.9	100
WS&F	5.2	32.8	62.1	100	16.1	35.7	48.2	100	14.3	23.2	62.5	100
SO&RF	1.8	19.3	78.9	100	3.6	27.3	69.1	100	1.8	21.4	76.8	100
Store	13.5	48.1	38.5	100	22.6	41.5	32.8	100	14.8	46.3	38.9	100
Transport S.	13.0	31.5	55.6	100	23.1	36.5	40.4	100	23.1	35.2	44.4	100
S& safety	20.4	40.7	38.9	100	13.0	33.3	53.7	100	15.8	42.1	42.1	100
Average	17.65	36.99	45.17	100	21.19	36.06	42.14	100	19.82	36.38	43.98	100

Note:

- SF – T stands for Sanitation facilities e.g. Toilet
- CMF stands for Clinic or medical facilities
- WS&F stands for Water supply& facilities, and
- SO&RF stands for Student organizations and recreational facilities e.g. Tennis, sport fields, etc.
- Transport S. stands for Transport Service
- S& Safety stands for Security& safety

Table 12: Learning Resources Sufficiency and Adequacy – The Administration Staffs Response

Facilities	Accessibility				Utilization				Quality			
	High	Moderate	Low	Total	High	Fair	Poor	Total	Good	Less	Poor	Total
Library	10.5	44.7	44.7		28.9	34.2	36.8		31.7	36.6	31.7	
CC– Hardware	2.8	13.9	83.3		2.7	21.6	75.7		8.3	19.4	72.2	

⁷Valid percent were used for data analysis of the respondents

Internet Serv.	-	19.4	80.6		10.5	23.7	65.8		8.1	24.3	67.6	
Laboratories	-	8.3	91.7		5.6	13.9	80.6		5.7	14.3	80.0	
Workshops	-	16.7	83.3		11.1	13.9	75.0		8.6	14.3	77.1	
Auditorium	-	12.1	87.9		3.0	24.2	72.7		3.1	25.0	71.9	
D-Farms/Plant	-	31.3	68.8		8.6	37.1	51.4		11.8	23.5	64.7	
C – Services	-	37.5	62.5		12.1	27.3	60.6		17.6	29.4	52.9	
Remedial C	10.3	48.3	41.4		16.1	41.9	41.9		25.8	35.5	38.7	
C - materials	3.0	60.6	36.4		15.2	45.5	39.4		30.3	42.4	27.3	
Tutorials	15.2	51.5	33.3		18.8	40.6	40.6		23.5	41.2	35.3	
Financial sup.	14.7	29.4	55.9		21.9	37.5	40.6		28.6	31.4	40.0	
Average												

Note:

- CC –Hardware stand for Computer center with appropriate software and hardware, audio-visual
- C – Service stands for counseling services
- D – Farms/Plant stands for Demonstration Farms/Plant
- Remedial C stands for Remedial Courses
- C – Materials stand for Courses materials
- Financial sup. Stands for Financial support

Table 13: Physical Facilities – The Instructors Response⁸

Facilities	Accessibility				Utilization				Quality			
	High	Moderate	Low	Total	High	Fair	Poor	Total	Good	Less	Poor	Total
Classrooms	25.0	50.0	25.0		15.8	63.1	21.1		31.6	52.6	15.8	
Offices	-	36.8	63.2		5.3	47.4	47.4		-	38.9	61.1	
Lecture hall	10.0	40.0	50.0		5.3	42.1	52.6		15.8	36.8	47.4	
Dining hall	-	52.6	47.4		-	52.9	47.1		11.8	29.4	58.8	
Furniture	10.5	26.3	63.2		11.1	16.7	72.2		16.7	22.2	61.1	
SF – T	5.0	20.0	75.0		-	22.2	77.8		-	21.1	78.9	
CMF	-	35.0	65.0		-	44.4	55.6		5.3	21.1	73.7	
Cafeteria	-	36.8	63.2		6.3	25.0	68.8		5.9	23.5	70.6	
Dormitories	23.5	41.2	35.3		20.0	40.0	40.0		18.8	37.5	43.8	
Sport field	5.3	21.1	73.7		5.9	17.6	76.5		-	-	100	
WS&F	-	10.5	89.5		-	23.5	76.5		-	16.7	83.3	
SO&RF	-	-	100		-	17.6	82.4		-	11.1	89.9	
Store	5.6	55.6	38.9		11.8	41.2	47.1		6.3	50.0	43.8	
Transport S	15.8	57.9	26.3		6.3	62.5	31.3		37.5	31.3	31.3	
S& safety	5.6	33.3	61.1		6.3	31.3	62.5		6.3	31.3	62.5	
Average												

Note:

⁸Valid percent were used for data analysis of the respondents

- SF – T stands for Sanitation facilities e.g. Toilet
- CMF stands for Clinic or medical facilities
- WS&F stands for Water supply& facilities, and
- SO&RF stands for Student organizations and recreational facilities e.g. Tennis, sport fields, etc.
- Transport S. stands for Transport Service
- S& Safety stands for Security& safety

Table 14: Learning Resources Sufficiency and Adequacy – The Instructors Response

Facilities	Accessibility				Utilization				Quality			
	High	Moderate	Low	Total	High	Fair	Poor	Total	Good	Less	Poor	Total
Library	-	41.2	58.8		-	47.1	52.9		6.3	25.0	68.8	
CC– Hardware	-	11.1	88.9		-	5.6	94.4		-	22.2	77.8	
Internet serv.	-	15.8	84.2		-	26.3	73.7		-	21.1	78.9	
Laboratories	-	10.5	89.5		-	10.5	89.5		-	11.1	88.9	
Workshops	-	11.1	88.9		5.6	5.6	88.9		5.9	5.9	88.2	
Auditorium	-	-	100		-	5.3	94.7		-	11.1	88.9	
D–Farms/Plant	-	15.8	84.2		5.3	10.3	84.2		-	11.1	88.9	
C – Services	5.6	16.7	77.8		-	22.2	77.8		-	23.5	76.5	
Remedial C	-	50.0	50.0		5.6	44.4	50.0		-	47.1	52.9	
C/materials	-	31.6	68.4		-	47.4	52.6		-	52.6	47.4	
Tutorials	10.5	63.2	26.3		-	70.0	30.0		11.1	55.6	33.3	
Financial sup.	-	33.3	66.7		-	33.3	66.7		-	43.8	56.3	
Average												

Note:

- CC –Hardware stand for Computer center with appropriate software and hardware, audio-visual
- C – Service stands for counseling services
- D – Farms/Plant stands for Demonstration Farms/Plant
- Remedial C stands for Remedial Courses
- C – materials stands for Courses materials
- Financial sup. Stands for Financial support

Table 15: Physical Facilities – The Students Response⁹

Facilities	Accessibility				Utilization				Quality			
	High	Moderate	Low	Total	High	Fair	Poor	Total	Good	Less	Poor	Total
Classrooms	37.9	51.8	10.3		45.8	44.0	10.2		56.1	31.6	12.3	

⁹Valid percent were used for data analysis of the respondents

Offices	32.1	46.4	21.4		33.3	48.1	18.5		44.6	42.9	12.5	
Lecture hall	28.6	30.3	41.1		41.5	22.7	35.8		35.2	35.2	29.6	
Dining hall	14.5	43.6	41.8		20.4	33.3	46.3		18.5	40.7	40.7	
Furniture	23.2	35.7	41.1		27.5	31.4	41.2		33.3	44.4	22.2	
SF – T	5.4	25.0	69.6		9.1	29.1	61.8		1.8	31.6	66.7	
CMF	6.9	44.8	48.3		12.5	35.7	51.8		10.5	47.4	42.1	
Cafeteria	12.5	39.3	48.2		8.8	49.1	42.1		8.9	30.4	60.7	
Dormitories	33.9	51.8	14.3		31.6	49.1	19.3		44.6	35.8	19.6	
Sport field	15.8	15.8	68.4		8.9	32.1	58.9		10.3	32.8	56.9	
WS&F	5.2	32.8	62.1		16.1	35.7	48.2		14.3	23.2	62.5	
SO&RF	1.8	19.3	78.9		3.6	27.3	69.1		1.8	21.4	76.8	
Store	13.5	48.1	38.5		22.6	41.5	35.8		14.8	46.3	38.9	
Transport S	13.0	31.5	55.6		23.1	36.5	40.4		20.4	35.2	44.4	
S& safety	20.4	40.7	38.9		13.0	33.3	53.7		15.8	42.1	42.1	
Average												

Note:

- SF – T stands for Sanitation facilities e.g. Toilet
- CMF stands for Clinic or medical facilities
- WS&F stands for Water supply& facilities, and
- SO&RF stands for Student organizations and recreational facilities e.g. Tennis, sport fields, etc.
- Transport S. stands for Transport Service
- S& Safety stands for Security& safety

Table 16: Learning Resources Sufficiency and Adequacy – The Students Response

Facilities	Accessibility				Utilization				Quality			
	High	Moderate	Low	Total	High	Fair	Poor	Total	Good	Less	Poor	Total
Library	9.3	46.3	44.4		20.0	47.3	32.7		16.7	46.3	37.0	
CC– Hardware	3.4	8.6	87.9		6.8	23.7	69.5		5.2	20.7	74.1	
Internet serv.	13.8	84.5	1.7		3.4	29.3	67.2		1.7	27.6	70.7	
Laboratories	1.8	15.8	82.5		3.4	24.1	72.4		3.6	21.4	75.0	
Workshops	-	18.2	81.8		5.4	23.2	71.4		5.4	23.2	71.4	
Auditorium	4.0	34.0	62.0		11.8	27.5	60.8		3.9	39.2	56.9	
D-Farms/Plant	9.1	16.4	74.5		11.1	20.4	68.5		12.7	21.8	65.5	
C – Services	11.1	37.0	51.9		16.4	41.8	41.8		20.0	32.7	47.3	
Remedial C	11.5	28.8	59.6		11.5	40.4	46.2		19.2	26.9	53.8	
C/materials	19.6	44.6	35.7		25.5	40.0	34.5		26.8	41.1	32.1	
Tutorials	16.4	43.6	40		22.4	50.0	27.6		22.4	46.6	31.0	
Financial sup.	7.1	35.7	57.1		10.7	39.3	50.0		14.8	25.9	59.3	
Average												

Note:

- CC –Hardware stand for Computer center with appropriate software and hardware, audio-visual
- C – Service stands for counseling services
- D – Farms/Plant stands for Demonstration Farms/Plant
- Remedial C stands for Remedial Courses
- C – materials stands for Courses materials
- Financial sup. Stands for Financial support

From the respondents i.e. administration staffs, Instructors and Students physical facilities such as class rooms (73.1%), lecture halls (72.8%) and dormitories (74.5%) have scored moderate to high responses on average in their accessibility, utilization and quality respectively (see table 11, 13 and 15). Others like Offices, Dining halls, Furniture, Sanitation facilities, Clinic/medical facilities, Cafeteria, Sport field, Water supply & facilities, Student organizations and Recreational facilities, Store, Transport service Safety and security got either low or poor remarks from our respondents in terms their accessibility, utilization and quality (see table 11,13 and 15). The average Class-student ratio is calculated to be around 1:39 which talk that the university is closer to the national standard requirement ratio in comparison.

The overall response obtained indicates that both learning resources and educational facilities such as Library, Computer center with appropriate software and hardware, audio-visual, Internet service, Laboratories, Workshops, Auditorium, Demonstration Farms/Plant, Counseling services, Remedial courses, Course materials, Tutorials and Financial support got either low or poor remarks in rating.

Observation of facilities like classrooms, library, laboratory, cafeteria and clinic tells various prospects. For examples, classrooms lack necessary ventilation and are subjected to sound pollution. They are not equipped with quality teaching boards, projectors, teaching aids, etc. however, there enough number of chairs in respective classes. In principle, the library is supposed to accommodate 25% of the total students which is currently amount to 506 and the library expert claims that the existing hall have a capacity of 500 at once but actual count indicates that only 263 of persons can be service at a time. There is no data available for books and reference books according to each department. It is observed that there is no qualify and sufficient manpower serving the library at the moment. The University has nine laboratory rooms and none of them have sufficient required facilities and materials but Soil, Animal, Computer, and GIS laboratories have better facilities as compare to others.

Clinic has better drug supplies with less sufficient laboratory re-agents or materials and equipment's like Microscope. There are no working manuals and procedures for professional reference and support. The Cafeteria is highly unhygienic with shortages of cooking supplies and well-connected water points.

Most students (71.2%), academic and administration staffs (60.9%) are dissatisfy on utilization of the University educational resources and facilities. Regarding resources and facilities maintenance and updating mechanisms, 68.8% and 62.5% of staffs and 59.3% and 40.7% of students are unsatisfied. 46.9% of the respondents believes that the budget allocated is enough and adequate to run their program. Paradoxically, 40.6% of respondents do not. The budget allocations against

forecast in the last two years, 35.9% have rejected the matching relation and 34.4% commended the existence of matching. The employee discontent were basically claimed to link to decentralized use of budget utilization and lack of empowerment to the concerned work units as observed from the survey questionnaires, interviews and focus group discussions as well.

According to the department experts, there is no institutionalized mechanism for expenditure and budget forecast so far. In the current fiscal budget year request was benchmarked by adding 20% on past budget year for forecast. The total budget were allocated for academic (60%), research (9%), for community service (6%), and administration (25%). However, this have some problems in practices of implementation and utilization as there is usually unexpected and unplanned budget requisites and transfers from the management council and other work units from one budget code to another that creates inconsistency in budget plan.

4.1.4. Academic and Support Staffs

The University is basically administered by two components, the Academic and Administration lines of staffs. The Academics stream as total of 230 staffs (i.e. instructors, Graduates Assistants, technical assistant). For more details kindly refer to the below Tables.

Table 17: Academic Staffs Data by Faculty/School

Academic Units	PhD	MSc/MA	BSc/BA/DVM	Technical Ast Diploma	Total
College of Agri. N. Resource*	6	51	55	8	120
Faculty of Business& Economic	10	22	16	2	50
Faculty of HCSc.**	-	27	20	-	47
Faculty of Engineering	-	3	6	-	9
School of Law	1	1	2	-	4
Total	17	104	99	10	230

*Agr. N. Resources = Agriculture and Natural Resources

**HCSc. = Humanities and Computational Science

Table 18: Academic-Staff Expatriate-local Mix

Staff Category	Sex	PhD	MSc/MA	BSc/BA/DVM	Technical Ass. Diploma	Total	%
Expatriate	M	11	4	-	-	15	
	F	2	2	-	-	4	
Sub-total		13	6	-	-	19	
Local	M	4	91	85	9	189	
	F	-	7	14	1	22	
Sub-total		4	98	99	10	211	
Total		17	104	99	10	230	

Table 19: Academic-Staff On-Job-Study Leave Ratio

Staff Category	Sex	PhD	MSc/MA	BSc/BA/DVM	Technical Ast Diploma	Total	%
On Leave	M	14	46	8	-	68	
	F	2	2	1	-	5	
Total		16	48	9	-	73	
On Job	M	15	81	39	1	136	
	F	2	7	12	-	21	
Total		17	88	51	1	157	
Expected Total		33	136	60	1	230	

Table 20: Academic-Staff Male-Female Ratio

Staff	Sex	PhD	MSc/MA	BSc/BA/DVM	Technical Asst Diploma	Total	% Female
On Job	F:M	2:15	7:81	12:39	0:1	21:136	13.38
Study Leave	F:M	2:14	2:46	1:8	0:0	5:68	6.85
Total	F:M	2:15	9:95	14:85	1:9	26:204	11.30

Table 21: Summary of Administration staffs and students

Sex	Administration		Academic	Student		
	Fixed	Contract		Regular	Summer	Weekend
M			204	1178	557	961
F			26	846	88	323
Total	355	211	230	2024	645	1284

Table 22: Academic staff-student ratio for each program

Faculty	Instructor	Student						Average Ratio
		Regular	Summer	Weekend	Regular	Summer	Weekend	
College of Agri. N Resource	120	653	1:5	507	1:4	452	1:4	1:13
Faculty of Business& Econ.	50	852	1:17	121	1:2	640	1:13	1:32
Faculty of HCSc**	47	383	1:8	-	-	153	1:3	1:11
Faculty of Engineering	9	43	1:5	-	-	39	1:4	1:9
School of Law	4	93	1:23	17	1:4	-	-	1:28
School of Graduate Studies		-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Average Total	230	2024	1:9	645	1:3	1284	1:6	1:17
Actual Average Ratio	156	2024	1:13	645	1:4	1284	1:8	1:25
Average Standard Ratio	101	2024	1:20	645	1:6	1284	1:13	1:39

Note: Technical assistant = 10 (2 in business and 8 in Agriculture), Graduate assistance = 99, and study-leave = 73 (16 PhD, 48MA/MSc, 9BA/BSc) = 74 and 55 Graduate assistance are on-job.

*Agr. N. Resources = Agriculture and Natural Resources and HCSc. = Humanities and Computational Science

As table indicates, the academic staff – student ratio can be viewed or depicted in three dimensions. First, the total number of academic staffs including instructors, graduates, and technical assistants against total number of students is calculated that is about 1:9 meaning one (1) instructor to nine (9) students. Second, the total numbers of the academic staffs that are on duty is calculated excluding the numbers of staffs on study-leave, and technical assistant who are not involved in actual teaching roles which is designated as Actual Average Ratio has resulted into 1:13 (one (1) instructor to thirteen (13) students). The third dimension relates to the academic staffs’ ratio of qualify staff which are supposed to involved in teaching roles as per national guidelines that excludes graduates assistant from instructors roles. In this regards, the average ratio resulted in 1:20 i.e. one (1) instructor to twenty (20) students. For general consideration, the average lecturer-student standard ratio for all students (i.e. regular, summer, and weekend) is about 1:39.

Table 23: Teaching Staff – level of qualification mix

Total	BSc/BA/DVM	MSc/MA	PhD
156	51	88	17
Ratio	33	56	11
Standard	0	70	30
Variance	-33	+14	+19

As indicated from the above Table 23, the university Teaching staff qualification mix or ratio is 33:56:11 which below national standard (0:70:30) set by MoE.

So far, the universities legislation and academic staff recruitment guideline (which is adopted from Mettu University) are used as major academic staffs' appointment documents. In the case of staff promotion the university is supposed to employ Harmonized Academic Policy of Ethiopian Public Higher Education institutions (February 2013) and GmU's Legislation (May 2015) as guiding tools to grant staff promotions. However, no academic staff promotion has been made since its establishment. In the case of supporting staffs, the appointment and promotion is consistent with federal ministry of civil service parameters.

In regard to staff appraisal system, higher officials, stakeholders, students, and colleagues are involved in evaluation process of the staffs. So far, the University has move to an inch by offering award and gifts to employees in both units. But there are claims that no proper and consistent staff appraisal system and evidence used. Records showed that, various training such as pedagogy induction, research methodology, BSC, Kaizen, etc and plans do exist for the institution.

4.1.5. Student Admission and Support Services

Various written policies and guidelines on student admission and support services do exist. Admission of newly student(s) can be through two means – national harmonized policy set by Ministry of Education for regular program that is entailed under article 35(1),(2) and second is granted through Continuous and Distance Education Program (CDEP) that reveals that admission to all full time and part-time which is approved by Senate as provided in University Legislation article 63 and article 36 under harmonized policy. Survey shows that 81.4% of the students from all programs are aware of the university admission policies through mass media, brochures and notices by Registrar and CDEP Coordination Offices. Through Office of Registrar the data of new entrance are posted and disseminated to concerns departments and units' staffs for further documentation and actions and these attainment of entering students data are used to inform teaching.

Students' support services are provided by various concerned units or departments and different platforms are arranged for students' academic counseling. In the survey, it's noted that 50.8% and 40.7% of the students confirmed the availability of the counseling and their satisfaction on academic counseling service respectively. Around 78% of the students acknowledged the existence of formal mechanism for representative students' voice to be heard. However, only 25% of the students have rated the effectiveness of the system, 37% have valued less and 32% have marked the 'student view consideration' as poor.

4.1.6. Program Relevance and Curriculum

As previously discussed, Gambella University has institutionalized system for program approval, monitoring and review that are adopted from various sources. For instance, article 58 of University Legislation has entails how the “Program Development and Review” is enacted¹⁰. However, there is no much more activities done so far that would serve as evidence that system are used systematically and to evaluates its effectiveness. Most of the newly opened programs are solely adopted from national harmonized curriculums and no evidence of external input though the manual allows up to 20% deviation from national standard.

Besides curriculums aims and objectives, the statement of aims and objective in each programs are stipulated involving the inclusion of transferable skill. These are formulated or contextualized in way that response to institutional aspiration, regional demands and national needs. The newly enrolled students are oriented and aware of the aims and objectives of their program every year before they are registered.

4.1.7. Teaching, Learning and Assessment

From the survey taken, the instructors response on “agree” and ‘strongly agree” scaled 55% and 65% respectively while it’s obtained that 71.2% of the students believes that courses are well structured to achieve the learning outcomes (meaning, there was a good balance of lectures, tutorials, practical etc.), and 80% are satisfied with the learning and teaching methods that encouraged participation.

On student view, 69.5% of the respondents marked that the teacher creates a safe and pleasant learning environment while 88.1% believed that the instructors used teaching methods (i.e. discussion, lecture, demonstration, etc.) that enhances learning in line with Instructors response that scored 83.3% and 85% accordingly. Regarding the Instructors appropriate and effective use of innovative technology, 50.9% agree and strongly agreed but only 31.1% of student respondents appreciated the existence of appropriate resources for practical education such as laboratory rooms while instructors indicate 50% and 25% on similar trends. However, the instructors and students response on the employment of variety and appropriate teaching-learning methods in the classes closely maintained positive outcomes at 80% and 77.9% respectively.

71.2% of the responded students feel welcome when seeking help or academic advice in or outside of class and 66.1% confirmed that Instructors are adequately accessible to students during office hours or after class meanwhile the instructor assessment result has come 85% and 79% accordingly. Close to half (50.9%) assured that Instructors often employ the implementation of theory into practice and contrast their implications, 69.4% presented the background or origin of ideas /concepts and their applicability in class, and 59.3% of the respondents informed that teaching enhanced their critical thinking and skills of scientific investigation. On similar issues, 57.9% of the instructors designated that theory is link to practices while they scored 89.5% on concepts applicability and approaches that enhance students’ critical thinking and skills of scientific investigation.

¹⁰ Also see Harmonized Academic Policy for Ethiopian Public Higher Education Institutions, February 2013.

Around 59% respondents informed that Instructors provides scientific information that allows them to gain a better and deeper understanding of the subject matter and the same figures response that the course integrates theoretical course concepts with real-world applications, a survey questions that instructors have comparatively scaled with 85% and 79%. Pertaining to grading continuous assessment, instructors marked higher score of 89.1% and 94% while 79% of the respondents of students are found aware of the grading system of Gambella University and 84.8% testified the Instructors use different methods of continuous assessments and final exams that matched with their course and program objectives. On the relevant and fair process of continuous assessment and final exam marking and grading procedures, 84.8% of the survey data and 59.4% of the respondents witnessed that there is problem solving procedures in department(s) and have got the opportunity to discuss the academic challenges with instructors. On this regards, instructors marked their satisfaction with 84.2 and 63.1% respectively. Finally, survey indicates that 74.4% of the students also bear out that their respective departments or instructors have informed or oriented them about appeal procedures while instructor confirmed their commitment in offering the task by 72.2%.

In general, questionnaires used to assess and evaluate the teaching, learning, and assessment of the institution, on average 67.7% of the students' respondents had positively either 'agree' or 'strongly agree' on the subject that show the positive step toward the University performance of this particular focus area.

In the interviews, it's confirmed that comprehensive evaluation tools are in place to evaluate teaching learning approach that involves first day first class, absenteeism, etc evaluation. Daily follow up are also made or conducted based on received complaints from students or from other sources. However, continuous assessment is a science by itself students, teachers and deans are aware and encouraged to do so. But there is no enough effort made to install the ownership in all parties.

4.1.8. Student Progression and Graduates Outcomes

Majority of students enrolled make good progress in their courses and most of the Graduates have managed to complete their programs effectively. However, a limited attrition rate is observed that is basically classified under four reasons: un-registered disappearance and absents; transfer cases to other universities; health related withdrawal; and academic dismissal cases besides unexpected disciplinary cases. Registrar Office data confirmed that the attrition figure is declining from time to time due to various remedial actions taken. Such remedial actions involve the tutorials classes that reduced the attrition that are related to academic dismissals. Transfers cases are also being filtered from cases to cases and from 150 request of transfer last year only 20 of them were allowed to get transfer. Moreover, in the 2015/16 academic year more than 100 and this year (2016/17) around 60 have not shown up for registration. But academic dismissal is low and they are supported in various ways that do not undermine the quality of the education. Readmission is also alternative or option to students who have shown low performance in their academic grades. For instance, in 2015/16, around twelve (12) students were readmitted and no much about drop out data nor established system to trace the Graduate students.

Table 24: Graduate Students' Data

Year	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
2007 (2014/5)	115	57	172
2008 (2015/6)	156	87	243
Grand total			415

Gambella University has no comprehensive data pool (rate of employment of graduate) regarding the graduates' destination and no role played to maximize job opportunity to the graduate so far. Two batches comprising of 415 students have been graduated.

Gambella University has not yet established any linkage with potential employers of its graduates but has built good networks with potential partners such as fellow Universities, Regional Disaster and Risk Management, and Office of Wildlife and Ecotourism, etc. As Gambella University is at infancy stage, it has not ever conducted a survey on the graduates work performance from their respective employer organization and there is no strong system established for foreign institutions networking and partnership.

4.1.9. Research and Outreach Activities

There is little progress on institutional affiliation with local, international academic institutions and industries to strengthen mutual benefit in regard to research, education and outreach activities. According to interview results, some degree of relationship is being cemented with bodies such as Regional Bureau of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Center, Office for Wildlife, etc. but the University need to go further to ensure effective Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) to pursue its operationalization with various stakeholders.

In the survey, the respondent's evaluation on frequency of workshops and seminars was 54.7%, and level of the staff involvement as organizers composed of 54.7%. The involvement of respondents as participants was 56.3% while relevance of research outputs and its problem-solving nature sum up from 'good' to 'excellent' with 59.4 %. On other hand, students grade the frequency of seminars and workshops with 52.6% (majority scored good with 33.9% of the total), their involvement on average is 59.3%, while relevance of research outputs and problem-solving nature has scored 62.7% (mostly of which the respondents scoring very good with 30.5%).

Gambella University has been committed to offer outreach and community services to Commercial Banks and Insurance companies particularly in area of recruitment of qualify staffs whereby the University liaised with beneficiaries on delivering the Exam to shortlisted candidates for final job selection. Training was given on concept and application of entrepreneurship to forty (40) disable persons from Gambella town in cooperation with Regional Labor and Social Affairs Agency. However, there is neither data available on research publications and/or would-be published works in the coming 12months nor numbers and nature of the academic institutions in partnerships with University.

4.1.10. Internal Quality Assurance

Various Internal quality assurance policy and guidelines that are adopted from Partner Universities are in place. However, these documents have remains on drafts and were disseminated for operationalization pending of the official approval of the Senate and concern organs. So far, there is no Program evaluation and action taken and there is no concrete future plan observed in the coming 12 months.

From the survey, the existence of education relevance and quality assurance institutional policy is confirmed by 68.8% of the respondents from administration staffs and instructors. Students respondents who are aware of the existence of committees and individuals or focal person in each department that are responsible to ensure the internal quality of the education is about 50.8% in comparison to 73.4% of the instructors' responses. However, its functionality to the administration staffs and instructors was 51.6% (mostly 'good' rates 34.4%) while 55.9% of the students confirmed that the functionality of the system is good.

Concerned Officers in the Directorate, expressed the need to undertake overall institutional quality assurance and check-up. On this regards, the Office has been engaged in developing and adopting quality assurance tools and delivering it for the concerned academic units. Informal inspections have been done in collaboration with units to minimize academic quality related issues like teachers' absenteeism, etc. Beyond the aforementioned effort there was no systematical data collection undertaken other than this document.

Based on the respondents' feedback, "there was no significant action that can be mentioned as a good practice; however, the current commitment to investigate the existing performance, gaps and related challenges is one of best institutional initiative that brought the courage to finalize this Self-Evaluation Audit". As there was no institutional audit carried out since its establishment, good practice was not institutionally scrutinized for dissemination. But, the ongoing SED preparation comprises the hope for possible identification of the existing good practices in the next 12 months.

4.1.11. Cross-Cutting Issues

The ESDP V has stipulated the cross-cutting issues as one of the four priority action programs in which Higher Education Institution are expected to consider and incorporated into their mainstreamed tasks.

4.1.11.1. Gender Sensitivity

As commented by the top management team, Gambella University has taken measure to institutionalize and strengthen the gender offices, gender forums, girls' clubs and female student associations. This is enacted in two main stream that involves Female employee (in particular Instructors) empowerment to leadership position and female students support services. On this regards, procedural document like guidelines, Code of Conduct or manuals on gender-mainstreaming and life skills training issues have been developed to action and noticeable initiatives to support female students' achievement through tutorial classes have also been conducted.

To ensure the participatory empowerment, the University managed to recruit female graduates and send many of them to school for capacity building and grading by adopting active affirmative action's and support programs from other Universities. However, there is no strong Women Club established to develop their skills and leadership to be competent at managerial level and tutorial classes. Besides, academic support, the University has been providing financial and material supports for with low socio-economic status.¹¹

4.1.11.2. Student with Special Needs

Special Need Students support service was not strongly in plan in past two years, however, recent assessment indicates that the issues are getting attention in institutional programs and in areas of building construction as well. This emerged as a result of unexpected enrollment of one 'blind student' last year. The University provided materials, hiring assistant on teaching-learning activities, psychological counseling and providing suitable place in dormitory.

4.1.11.3. HIV/AIDS Counseling and Support

Base on recent directives from Ministry of Education, the University has streamlined the course into curriculum of all departments. It comprises, HIV/AIDS, Reproductive Health, Gender based-Violence, and Life skill that is effected this academic year in some of the academic departments. However, this will be fully adopted next year. Life skill development is on progress and training was given last year but full time Counselor is not yet assigned for counseling services.

4.1.11.4. Environmental Control

Besides regular teaching-learning activities, students and staffs are encouraged to engage themselves in co-curricular of environment activities. Environmental club is formed and plan to plant various seedling in the University campus. Effort are also undertaken to raise the public awareness on environmental education and protection and to promote essential linkage between the environment and development. There is also a plan from the university to engage students in improving the quality and resilience of local environment and to play its role in the management of natural resources to promote sustainable socio-economic development. However, the ownership and operationalization as so far been the major challenges though the region has potential resources.

4.1.11.5. Drug and Substance Abuse (DSA)

It's learned that Gambella University has taken an initiative and effort to create conducive learning environment that is free from DSA. Consultation is made with Town Municipality and Administration to closely work on activities to tackle the problems starting from community based awareness. Evening attendance and student's roll calls is to be enacted by Procter Unit in the dormitories. Cross-cutting issues are not a responsibility of one Directorate but a multi-sectoral fact that need integrated and coordination efforts among agencies. One of the top management organs in his conclusion remark suggested that "All university community needs to take part

¹¹ This is basically done in cooperation with individual and corporate stakeholders. Beneficiaries also include male students who are identified as in need.

sketching solutions and ownership starting from the top management and incorporate them into curricula as these are viral and unavoidable to quality education achievement and should be considered for implementation.” Moreover, this conceptual tool will enable graduates to be acquainted with upcoming challenges in their life and future careers.

4.2. Good Practices

From the discussions with Higher Officials, it’s learned that the administration was in havoc with the students at the start on various issues including shortage of clean water, poor cafeteria service, weather hardship for the students, etc. that use led into complaints and protest. However, the University makes a close tie with state Administration that enables them to address the students’ demand. The multilateral integration and cooperation between the University and regional administration organs and stakeholders is one of the good practices that empower the University resilience to cope with majors challenges encountered especially in health and safety. For examples, the ad hoc provision of medical supplies and clean water by Regional Health Bureau and Water Development Bureau could be one of the few to be mention.

On other hand, being one of the recent established Universities in marginalize periphery combined with hard tropical climates, Gambella is prone to tropical diseases like malaria. Pertaining to these core challenges, the University has been in constant struggle to maintain peace and stability among its community that has been temporal and national threats to many fellow institutions. This task was ensured in close coordination and cooperation with regional administration and Gambella community by large. The University was committed to tackle challenges related to campus safety by managing social harmony among students and by creating mutual understanding among the students from diverse ethnic communities to maintain peace and harmony. This is vital to the smooth flow of the academic programs without any interruption throughout the past. It is also accredited with peaceful co-existence of the students that have been major sources of violent protest in many parts of the countries.

Above all, the students resilience characters to stood up in challenging situation in time has created an opportunity for leadership to look into internal challenges and turns them into positive hallmark for peaceful learning environment. And this was translated into admirable practice that its exposure has to be extended to others.

Home grown financial software’s like FPCS and BCRRS are used as a tools to enhance the financial flow and budget control for the University.

5. Conclusion

The University is envisioned to be one of the Africa recognized academics and research centers by 2030 that aims to meet national and regional development needs. It has various policies documents concerning its vision, mission, and goal which most of university community seem to be aware of their existence. However, these documents lack consistency in contents and values. For example, it is observed that the Strategic Plan stipulated twelve goals while an annual plan has seventeen goals. In additions, the University mission is presented inconsistently in various published documents that proved it’s incoherent.

The University has functional governing organs and leadership that is regularly dealing with programs and day-to-day activities as proclaimed in various documents such as Senate Legislation and proclamation 650/2009. But the assessment shown that a significant numbers do not feel well presented in the decision making process that might links to lack of clear working structure and communication gaps on how decision are made.

Generally, there is a good trend on availability and provision of physical facilities such as classrooms, dormitories, and lecture halls that are observed to be in line with national standards that prove the good achievements made so far. HERQA standards classroom – student ratio in Engineering, language, and medicine and computer is about 1:20 and Business and law 1:40. Meanwhile Gambella University stood to be about 1:39 on average. Despite these encouraged achievements, the University is however lacking much in provision of quality of learning resources and some facilities such as laboratories, workshop, sanitation facilities, etc. Survey data evidenced that the University is on tract in the areas of academic and support staff services. For instances, the instructor-student mix is promising in some department and on average as well apart from poor academic professional mixed whereby most of the lecture fall in ranges of second degree and most of the PhD holders are expatriates. The academic staff female ratio is low that need further consideration.

The students are well informed on admissions but significant number of the respondents still protested their dissatisfaction on support and counseling services. The University has made exceled effort to ensure the program relevancy and quality education. But it noted that the policy documents and guidelines that are disseminated for the realization of this goal are not yet officially approved by the concerned bodies that questioned their authenticity. So far not many activities have been commenced in curriculum review and almost all programs are pursue based on national harmonized curriculum.

It is learned that ranges of teaching methods are being used to enhance the cognitive, affective and psycho-motor domain. Though class theoretical and concept presentation, continuous assessment, and grading system are appraised, the practical educations is questioned due to lack of related facilities like laboratories chemical, workshops and demonstration farms hardware's.

Concerning the students' progression and graduate's outcomes, good progress is observed on admission and completion rates. There are four basic factors that attribute to the attrition. These include unregistered disappearance and absents, transfer to other Universities, health related withdrawal, and academic dismissal. The University has drawn various mechanisms to address the problems which have shown the significant decline of dropout. However, the University has no any system that helps to trace the neither graduates students nor formal links with employers.

The University extended its partnership to fellow universities and other organizations that involve locals and international institutions as well, but more is still to be done to strengthen the linkages on research and community services. Survey indicates that many of the respondents are aware of the existence of the institutionalized bodies, policies and guidelines for internal quality assurance. Almost half of the survey population has doubted the functionality of the existing system which

could serve as the basic indicator for further steps in improvement of our stand to ensure the educational quality.

Regarding cross cutting issues that is known to play paramount role on the future development of the institution, it's learned that a lot are still to be done especially on gender sensitivity, student with special needs, HIV/AIDS and Reproductive health, and environmental issues not only in awareness creation but also and creating more opportunities in inclusive education in all aspect. More emphasizes is required on female students and staffs leadership empowerment and creating the drug free community in and around the University.

5.1. Plan for Enhancement of Processes and Practices

Considering its life span, Gambella University has made a good progress in the past two years and it could be appraised on the steps it took to attain its goals. Pertaining to this, the following recommendations are the major issues identified to address the existing challenges and operational gaps that need to be considered for improvement.

- The University needs to revisit its vision, mission, and goals as they lacks uniformity content and understandings in official documents and outlet such as Strategic Plan, Annual Plan, Newsletter, etc.
- With the exception of classrooms, dormitories, and lecture halls, the University has to fulfill its gaps in the provision of learning resources and infrastructure that are crucial and pivotal role for the institution future development.
- Classrooms, library, dormitories, laboratories, offices etc. ventilations has to be improved as they are not well designed to suit the weather situation in Gambella context to create a conducive teaching-learning and working environment. In additions, regular and timely maintenance, sustainable water supply and cleaning of the premises need to be considered. The Gambella University needs to upgrade its system of resources utilization, maintenance, updating mechanism using modern approaches like Kaizen.
- The university should emphasize provision of necessary facilities and supplies for practical education – workshops and laboratories need to equip with necessary materials and supplies. Besides, the University in its strategic plan has projected the enrollment to grow in exponential rate. It is therefore necessary to plan for infrastructures and facilities sustainable improvement and development in advance to contain the increasing enrollment rates.
- More recreational centers such basketball court, football field, cafeteria or lounge, etc. are required for both staffs and students to create healthy and friendly community to create a pleasant working environment.
- The university needs to constantly engage on assessment of curriculum review to ensure up-to-datedness of each program to be enable to revise and contextualized aims and objectives programs timely.
- The University needs to address the standards gaps in teaching staff professional mix ratios (0:70:30) and instructor-student ratio gaps that is observed in some faculties to improve its effort to attain the educational quality assurance. Moreover, staff retention policies need to be also placed to tackle possible brain drain.

- Research and community service need to be well organized to meet the need for timely problem-solving research and improved funding release procedures.
- The university has to advance its ICT infrastructure and sketch the system of communication to create the communication platforms with the graduates students and potential stakeholders via social media, Alumina, etc.
- The student council role is very important to ensure the participation of students in planning and decision making process. It's therefore needed to be strengthened and fully empower to engage in relevant institutional platforms. Parallel, alternative mechanisms and inclusive channels of communication are needed for staffs' members on how decisions are made by the management.
- The University needs to decentralize its financial planning and allocations of budget; and empower the work units in decision making, uses, and expenditure control of their respective budget besides applying appropriate budget formulation.
- Many university manuals, policies, guidelines, etc. produced and/or adopted for internal uses and functions need to be approved, labeled and legalized for publication and disseminated to users by the concerned bodies.
- The University needs to promote and disseminate its base practices for other fellow institutions and stakeholders.

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